

MONITORING OF NEPHROPATHIES IN DIABETES MELLITUS USING LABORATORY TESTS

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Annotation: The article considers clinical and laboratory changes in patients with nephropathy in type 2 diabetes mellitus, assessed using laboratory studies. It has been established that the presence of even minor renal dysfunction in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus can be diagnosed using laboratory tests. The obtained data emphasize the importance of prevention and prediction of the development of renal dysfunction, correction of risk factors and progression of nephropathy.

Key words: diabetic nephropathy, laboratory analysis, diabetes mellitus.

INTRODUCTION. The World Health Organization has officially recognized diabetes as an incurable disease at the modern level of medical science and clinical practice, charging the patient for a responsible attitude to their health[6]. Diabetic nephropathy is one of the most serious complications of diabetes mellitus, leading to early disability and death of patients from terminal renal failure [3]. The prevalence of diabetic nephropathy is continuously increasing, which is associated with the interaction of genetic and environmental factors in patients with both type 1 and type 2 diabetes mellitus [11]. Diabetic nephropathy in diabetes mellitus is characterized by damage to the arteries, arterioles, glomeruli and tubules of the kidneys, resulting from impaired metabolism of carbohydrates and lipids [12]. It is customary to distinguish three stages of diabetic nephropathy: the stage of microalbuminuria; the stage of proteinuria with preserved kidney function and the stage of chronic renal failure [10]. And only at the stage of microalbuminuria is it possible to prevent progression[9].The frequency of detection of diabetic nephropathy is closely dependent on the duration of diabetes mellitus, this dependence has been more studied in type 1 diabetes mellitus (insulin-dependent), due to a more accurate determination of the onset [13]. The formation of kidney damage in diabetes mellitus and the development of diabetic nephropathy is a continuously progressive multifactorial process, among the pathogenetic theories of which metabolic, hemodynamic and genetic are recognized as significant [5].

The incidence of diabetic nephropathy in patients with type 1 diabetes lasting up to 10 years is 5-6%, up to 20 years - 20-25%, up to 30 years – 35-40%, up to 40 years – 45%, the maximum peak in the development of diabetic nephropathy falls on the period from 15 to 20 years of diabetes mellitus [2]. In type 2 diabetes mellitus, the same dependence of the frequency of diabetic nephropathy on the duration of diabetes mellitus has been established [11].

PURPOSE: To evaluate the course of nephropathy in diabetes mellitus according to laboratory parameters.

MATERIALS AND METHODS. The study was performed on the basis of the Samarkand Regional Multidisciplinary Hospital, Department of Nephrology. To achieve this goal, a retrospective study was conducted from the patient chart in the period December 2021. The number of patients with nephropathy in diabetes mellitus is 20. Of these, 12 (60%) are men, 8 (40%) are women. The average age is 59.5. All patients

were examined: general clinical analysis, biochemical blood test, hepatitis B, C, D test. According to the presence of functional signs of kidney damage, 2 groups of patients were formed: group 1 – control group, patients without changes in functional markers of kidney damage - 20 patients (10 men and 10 women, average age 55.8); group 2 – patients with changes in functional markers of kidney damage - 20 patients (12 men and 8 women, the average age is 59.5).

Table 1 Distribution of patients by age and sex

№	Gender of the patient	Age, years		
		40-50	51-60	61-70
1	Women (n=8)	-	5	3
2	Men (n=12)	1	8	3
	Total	1	13	6

Diagram No. 1. Distribution of patients by gender and age

As can be seen from Table 1, the disease is common in both women and men, with a predominance in men, this is due to the anatomical features of the male sex and may be related to lifestyle.

The tests were performed on the following analyzers: General blood test "DIRUI BCC-3600", biochemical analyzes "Mindray BS -120", general urine analysis on the analyzer

"Mindray UA -66", enzyme immunoassay was performed "Mindray -96".

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: The main group included 20 patients with different course of nephropathy. All patients were examined: general clinical analysis, biochemical blood test, hepatitis B, C, D. The distribution of patients by age showed that 65% were in the age group of 50-60 years. This data indicates that up to one year and entering the next age group there is a predisposition to ICD.

5% - in under 50 years; 30% - in 60-70 years. There were 12 (60%) more men than 8 (40%) women. This is due to the anatomical features of the male sex and may be related to lifestyle.

The laboratory data of the patients are shown in Table 2 (Table 2).

Table 2. Clinical and laboratory indicators

Indicators	Results (Arithmetic mean)	Normal values
General blood test		
Erythrocyte sedimentation rate	47,6 mm/h	5 – 15 мм/ч
Hb	67,3 g/l	120-140 g/l
RBC	$3,21 \cdot 10^{12}/l$	$4,5-5,5 \cdot 10^{12}/l$
Color indicator	0,63	0,85-1,05
WBC	$8,17 \cdot 10^9/l$	$4,0 - 8,0 \cdot 10^9/l$
PLT	$211 \cdot 10^9/l$	$150-400 \cdot 10^9/l$
Биохимические показатели		
Urea	18 mmol/l	3,0 – 8,0 mmol/l
Creatinine	580 mkmol/l	53,3 – 100 mkmol/l
Total protein	55 g/l	65-85 g/l
Bilirubin	21,5 mkmol/l	3,7-21,7 mkmol/l
Direct bilirubin	2,68 mkmol/l	3-8,9 mkmol/l
Cholesterol	7,5 mmol/l	3.3-6,6 mmol/l
Alanine Aminotransferase	18,8 Ed/l	34-37 Ed/l
Aspartate Aminotransferase	22 Ed/l	40-45 Ed/l
General urine analysis		
Protein in urine	10,04 g/l	Absent
WBC under microscopy	10-14 In the field of view	2 – 3 In the field of view
RBC under microscopy	1-3-2 In the field of view	0 – 1 In the field of view
Enzyme immunoassay for viral hepatitis A, B, C		
Viral hepatitis “A”	Negative	Negative
Viral hepatitis “B”	Negative	Negative
Viral hepatitis “C”	Positive in one patient	Negative

The main group included 20 patients with different course of nephropathy. During clinical and laboratory examination, it turned out that in the general blood test, the rate of erythrocyte sedimentation in 18 (90%) patients was sharply increased. The number of erythrocytes was sharply reduced in 17 patients (85%), which is probably due to a decrease in the production of erythropoietin by the kidneys due to chronic kidney damage. The concentration of hemoglobin in the peripheral blood and color index in all patients was also reduced, which is associated with redistribution and increased consumption of iron from the depot. This shows that patients have hypochromic anemia. When studying the biochemical parameters of the serum of patients, it was found that creatinine and urea were sharply increased in 18 (90%) patients, due to a decrease in nitrogen excretion function of the kidneys. Total protein was lowered in 15 (75%) patients and cholesterol levels were elevated in all patients.

A general urine analysis revealed protein in high concentrations in 16 (80%) patients, leukocytes (WBC) in 7 (35%) patients and erythrocytes (RBC) in 8 (40%) patients in insignificant amounts.

The above changes indicate that in many patients in the main group, nephropathy is complicated by chronic renal failure in the terminal stage and uremia is detected in the blood of these patients, which requires certain therapeutic measures in order to improve the condition.

CONCLUSIONS

1. From the above, it can be concluded that in many patients in the main group, nephropathy is complicated by chronic renal failure in the terminal stage and uremia is detected in the blood of these patients, which requires certain therapeutic measures in order to improve the condition.
2. An increase to high numbers of protein in the urine is observed in all patients. This indicates that in many patients, the glomerular endothelium is severely damaged.
3. Follow-up of patients with diabetes mellitus should include the determination of indicators of general blood analysis, biochemical blood analysis (determination of creatinine, urea, total protein, cholesterol and low, high density lipoproteins, glucose, glycated hemoglobin), general urine analysis (mandatory determination of microalbumin), in order to prevent various complications.
4. Thus, studies show that using laboratory research methods, it is possible to assess the level of renal damage, monitor and predict the condition of a patient with nephropathy in diabetes mellitus.

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